

CURRENT APPROACHES IN ENDOMETRIAL CANCER: A REVIEW

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Endometrial carcinoma (EC) is increasingly stratified by molecular and immunohistochemical (IHC) features that state the prognosis and guide the personalized therapy. Histopathologically, IHC surrogates for TCGA-defined subtypes (POLE-mutated, MMR- deficient, p53-abnormal and NSMP) stratify the risk in EC.

Additional markers (ER, PR, and Ki-67) further tailor management. Epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) correlates with the myometrial invasion and metastasis. Hypoxia, via HIF-1- α overexpression, promotes angiogenesis and stem-like phenotypes in EC, detectable by IHC and linked to poor outcome. ARID-1A loss identifies a subset with distinct biological behaviour and potential sensitivity to epigenetic therapies. Integrating these markers into routine pathology practice will improve the precise personalized medicine.

Keywords: Endometrial cancer, TCGA, Epithelial-Mesenchymal Transition, Hypoxia.

Introduction

Endometrial carcinoma is the most common gynecologic malignancy in developed nations, with increasing incidence. Traditional histological classification (endometrioid vs. non endometrioid) and FIGO grade inadequately predict outcomes in up to 20% of cases. The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) molecular classification has been translated into IHC surrogates, improving prognostic accuracy and guiding adjuvant treatment. Beyond these, pathologists now routinely assess markers of proliferation (Ki-67), hormone receptors (ER, PR), EMT (E cadherin, Snail, Slug), hypoxia (HIF-1 α , GLUT 1), and chromatin remodeling (ARID1A) to refine risk and identify therapeutic targets.

1. Histopathology in endometrial cancer

Histopathologic evaluation remains the gold standard in endometrial cancer diagnosis, traditionally dividing tumors into type I (endometrioid, estrogen-driven, generally low-grade) and type II (non-endometrioid, high-grade, aggressive) categories based on morphology and grade [1]. However, considerable heterogeneity exists within these groups, and up to 20% of cases are misclassified by morphology alone, leading to imbalanced risk stratification [2].

To overcome these limitations, immunohistochemical (IHC) surrogates for the Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) Research Network molecular classification are progressively used routinely. Loss of one or more mismatch repair proteins (MLH1, MSH2, MSH6, PMS2) by IHC defines the MMR deficient (MMRd) subgroup, which comprises 13-30% of ECs and carries an intermediate prognosis with sensitivity to immune checkpoint blockage [3]. Aberrant p53 staining (overexpression or total absence) strongly correlates with tp53 mutation and identifies the p53 abnormal (p53-abn) high-risk subgroup, often seen in serous and grade 3 endometrioid carcinomas [4]. Cases with loss in MMRd and p53 abn patterns fall into the NSMP (no specific molecular profile) category, for which additional IHC markers guide the risk assessment [3].

Beyond molecular surrogates, pathologists routinely use hormone receptor (ER, PR) and proliferation

markers (Ki-67) with IHC. ER/PR positivity is characteristic of low-grade endometrioid EC and predicts response to progestin therapy, whereas PR loss is associated with higher grade and recurrence risk [5]. A Ki-67 index higher than 30% correlates with aggressive behavior and poor prognosis [6]. Finally, AT-rich interaction domain 1A gene (ARID1A) has been found mutated in all types of endometrium-associated tumors, including undifferentiated and dedifferentiated endometrial carcinomas [7].

2. Epithelial-Mesenchymal Transition (EMT)

Epithelial-mesenchymal transition is a dynamic process whereby epithelial tumor cells acquire mesenchymal characteristics, enabling the invasion and metastasis. Histologically, EMT is marked by the loss of membranous E-cadherin and gain of mesenchymal markers such as Vimentin and β -catenin, detectable by IHC [8]. In EC, decreased E-cadherin expression correlates with deep myometrial invasion and lymphovascular space involvement, hallmarks of aggressive behavior [9].

Key transcriptional regulators of EMT-Snail, Slug and ZEB1- are upregulated in high grade and metastatic EC. IHC studies show nuclear Snail/Slug staining in regions of E-cadherin loss, indicating direct transcriptional repression of cell-cell adhesion molecules [8]. ZEB1 overexpression is particularly prominent in type II and serous ECs and associates with chemoresistance and poor outcome [10].

Clinically, evaluation of EMT markers augments conventional grading. An EMT related IHC panel (E-cadherin, vimentin, Snail, ZEB1) stratifies patients into low and high metastatic risk groups more precisely than FIGO grade alone [11]. Incorporation of EMT status into pathology reports may identify patients who may benefit from more aggressive adjuvant therapy.

3. Hypoxia and HIF-1 α

Tumor hypoxia is a key driver of aggressive phenotype and therapy resistance in EC. Hypoxic regions stabilize hypoxia-inducible factor-1 α (HIF-1 α), a transcription factor that induces angiogenesis (via VEGF), metabolic reprogramming (GLUT-1), and stem-like traits [12]. IHC detection of HIF-1 α in >5% of tumor

nuclei reliably marks hypoxic adaptation. Additionally, staining with GLUT-1 further distinguishes metabolically active zones [13].

HIF-1 α shows significantly higher expression in recurrent endometrial carcinomas compared with their primary tumors. It is not yet an independent predictor of recurrent endometrial carcinomas [14]. This stabilization coincides with excessive microvascular proliferation – upregulation of VEGF downstream of HIF 1 α results in dense, immature capillary tufts that stain intensely for VEGF and CD31 but are not covered by mature α SMA-positive pericytes [15]. At the invasive front, histology reveals glandular disintegration and “budding” of single cells amidst desmoplastic stroma. IHC shows loss of membrane E cadherin, positive staining for Vimentin and N cadherin, and redistribution of β catenin from the membrane to the cytoplasm and nucleus, evidence of EMT activation under hypoxia [16]. Taken together, these histological patterns – perinecrotic foci, neovascular clusters and EMT-positive invasive fronts – together define the morphological fingerprint of HIF-1 α -induced adaptation in endometrial cancer and it can be reproducibly assessed by targeted IHC panels in routine diagnostic practice.

4. ARID1A in Endometrial Cancer

ARID1A encodes BAF250a, a critical SWI/SNF chromatin remodeling complex subunit that regulates gene expression through modulating nucleosome positioning [17]. IHC assessment of ARID1A reveals either complete loss or focal “clonal loss” patterns, both of which closely correspond to underlying ARID1A mutations [18]. Loss of ARID1A expression occurs in approximately 40-50% of endometrioid ECs and is enriched in MMRd/MSI H tumors, suggesting a cooperation between chromatin remodeling defects and genomic instability [19]. A study on early stage grade 3 endometrioid EC (G3EEC) shows that ARID1A loss predicts significantly longer recurrence free survival, independently of p53 or MMR status, indicating its potential as a favorable prognostic marker in selected high grade cases [20].

Discussion

The TCGA classification divides endometrial carcinomas into four molecular groups-POLE ultramutated, MMR deficient, p53 abnormal, and NSMP-each of which shows different morphologic trends. POLE ultramutated tumors often present with high-grade nuclear atypia but paradoxically favorable outcomes-they show dense tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes and prominent tumor budding on H&E, reflecting an active immune microenvironment [21]. MMR-deficient carcinomas often show mixed endometrioid and mucinous differentiation, prominent tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes, and peritumoral lymphoid cuffs. Loss of MLH1/PMS2 or MSH2/MSH6 by IHC confirms this subset [22]. The abnormal p53 group-grouping serous and some grade 3 endometrioid carcinomas-demonstrates papillary, micropapillary, or solid growth with marked pleomorphism and aberrant (overexpression or null) p53 staining [23]. NSMP tumors lacking these markers rely on conventional histological grading and additional im-

munohistochemistry (ER, PR, Ki 67) for risk stratification, often showing well-formed glands and lower mitotic indices [24].

Epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) is recognizable on H&E by the loss of cohesive glandular architecture at the invasive front, with single cell infiltration or small clusters amid desmoplastic stroma [25]. IHC reveals downregulation of membranous E-cadherin and upregulation of N-cadherin and vimentin in these regions [9]. Nuclear expression of the EMT inducing transcription factors Snail and Slug localizes to cells undergoing morphological transition, correlating with lymphovascular invasion [8]. Quantitative image analysis shows that EMT marker positive zones coincide with areas of higher histologic grade and microvascular proliferation, underscoring their role in promoting the invasive phenotype [26].

Regions of tumor necrosis and perinecrotic palisading on H&E suggest underlying hypoxia. IHC for HIF 1 α demonstrates strong nuclear and cytoplasmic staining in these zones, often adjacent to necrotic areas. Co-expression of GLUT 1 highlights metabolically reprogrammed cells thriving under low oxygen tension. Hypoxic foci often overlap with EMT positive invasive fronts, indicating cooperation between hypoxia and EMT programs in histological progression. The density of HIF 1 α -positive nuclei correlates with higher FIGO grade and deeper myometrial invasion on pathological review [15].

By mapping TCGA subtypes onto H&E and IHC patterns, pathologists can generate comprehensive reports which combine molecular risk with morphological context. For example, a p53 abnormal tumor with extensive HIF 1 α positivity and EMT marker expression implies a highly aggressive histological phenotype, even if residual glandular differentiation persists. Conversely, a POLE ultramutated case with brisk lymphocytes and minimal HIF 1 α staining may be downgraded in risk in spite of high nuclear grade. Standardized scoring systems for E-cadherin loss, HIF 1 α index, and ARID1A IHC are needed to harmonize reporting. Digital pathology and AI models trained on TCGA annotated slides have shown promise in automating detection of EMT and hypoxia features, strongly correlating with pathologist assessments [27].

Conclusion

Despite significant progress in integrating TCGA IHC surrogates, EMT markers and HIF 1 α assessment into endometrial carcinoma histopathology, inter-laboratory variability in scoring and reporting remains substantial. To achieve reproducible diagnostics, standardized protocols and consensus guidelines for IHC assays-including E-cadherin/Slug for EMT, HIF 1 α /GLUT 1 for hypoxia and ARID1A-must be developed and adopted broadly. Large prospective multicenter studies are required to correlate these histological biomarkers with patient outcomes and to validate their independent prognostic and predictive utility. The incorporation of digital pathology and AI-driven image analysis holds promise to harmonize biomarker quantification and uncover subtle morphologic patterns, but requires further technical refinement and clinical vali-

dation. Ultimately, a unified histopathologic framework combining molecular subtyping, EMT and hypoxia profiling, and ARID1A status will support more precise diagnostics and therapy.

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